

Evaluation of Teacher Empowerment Education Program 4th Batch in South Tangerang Using the Krikpatrick Model

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ABSTRACT

The Teacher Empowerment Program (PPGP) is a professional development initiative through education, training, and mentoring that focuses on instructional leadership to promote holistic growth and active, proactive participation of students. The program aims to actively develop educators to implement student-centered learning. This qualitative research employs a narrative approach. The research results show positive behavioral changes in teacher mover after completing PPGP, notably impacting the improvement of classroom learning quality and the cultivation of a learning culture among teachers within the school ecosystem. Although some schools have not fully optimized the growth of a learning culture among their teachers, they are moving in the right direction. Challenges and obstacles are inherent in transformation efforts, reinforcing the appropriateness of the Ministry of Education and Culture's decision to appoint Teacher Empowerment Program participants as school leaders. This move strengthens the force for change and minimizes resistance to or rejection of change.

INTRODUCTION

From the results of the grand theory conducted by the researcher, it is known that the Teacher Empowerment Program (PPGP) is one of the programs included in the Merdeka Belajar policy package and is part of the educational reform process towards a better change. Based on the launch video of this program, the Minister of Education and Culture stated that "PPGP is an education and training program for future education leaders. Teacher empowerers are agents who will become future candidates for school principals, school supervisors, and training program trainers " (General Directorate of Teachers and Education Personnel, 2020).

This program fundamentally transforms the centralized or centralized educational approach to reform that has been running so far into a more decentralized one by transferring autonomy and the zone of change to the smallest component of the education system, namely teachers. Through the Teacher Empowerment Program, teachers will be positioned as agents of renewal who play a crucial role in transforming the school culture to be more excellent and innovative (Makarim, 2020). Teacher Empowerers will contribute to advancing education in Indonesia by creating student-centered learning and driving a better education ecosystem through a change in the learning mindset (Syahril, 2020). Before being declared as a Teacher Empowerer, a teacher must first participate in and complete the PPGP, which lasts for 9 (nine) months. The existence of PPGP also simultaneously eliminates the School Principal Training (School Principal Training), as graduates of PPGP or Teacher Empowerers will become school principals. This is because the Ministry of Education and Culture expects a paradigm shift for school principals, no longer focusing on school administration but serving as instructional leaders who mobilize and cultivate a learning culture for their teachers.

The program with a bottom-up approach, which empowers teachers (small components in education) as change agents by empowering other teachers and providing Teacher Empowerers with the opportunity to become school principals and supervisors, can be considered something new. The researcher, who has been working as a teacher for 17 years since 2006, is experiencing a program like this for the first time. Usually, the development of teacher competencies is centralized, with the Ministry of Education and Culture assigning experts to improve the competencies of teachers in targeted areas. However, with the existence of the Teacher Empowerment Program (PPGP), graduates of PPGP, also known as Teacher Empowerers, will enhance and empower their fellow teachers. A similar program existed during the 2013 curriculum, called National Instructors, but this program differs from PPGP because teachers who become National Instructors are not required to become school principals or supervisors. In contrast, Teacher Empowerers are obliged to be appointed as school principals or supervisors as regulated by the Ministry of Education and Culture.

Based on the above, in the researcher's opinion, what the Ministry of Education and Culture is doing by implementing the Teacher Empowerment Program is very commendable and has the potential to transform education in

Indonesia. Many literatures suggest that a bottom-up approach is more effective than a top-down approach. However, not everyone shares the same opinion as the researcher. There is opposition to the Teacher Empowerment Program, even from teachers and the PGRI organization (source: Inews.com).

The doubt about the success of the Teacher Empowerment Program in producing Teacher Empowerers as change agents, future education leaders, and student-centered learning leaders is the main reason for the researcher to evaluate the implementation of the Teacher Empowerment Program. The evaluation model to be used by the researcher is the Kirkpatrick model, as this model analyzes behavior changes and results from participants after participating in PPGP. By obtaining the analysis results of whether there is a change in the behavior of Teacher Empowerers and whether there is a positive impact given by Teacher Empowerers for the transformation of education, especially within the school ecosystem, it is hoped that it can address the mentioned doubts and also provide input for the Ministry of Education and Culture for future program improvements.

METHODOLOGY

In evaluating the Teacher Empowerment Program using the Kirkpatrick model, the researcher employs a qualitative research method with a narrative approach. Qualitative research involves methods to explore and understand meanings attributed by individuals or groups to social or human issues (Creswell, 2014). Furthermore, Creswell (2014) explains that the qualitative research process involves essential efforts such as posing questions and procedures, collecting specific data from participants, analyzing data inductively from specific to general themes, and interpreting the meaning of data.

From the explanation of qualitative research above, which emphasizes exploration from an individual's perspective, it is highly suitable for the Kirkpatrick evaluation model. This model aims to understand or evaluate the program from the participants' individual viewpoints, focusing on behavior (behavioral changes after participating in education) and results (impact provided by participants post-education).

It should be noted that as of now, the Ministry of Education and Culture has conducted the Teacher Empowerment Program five times for the South Tangerang region, namely batches 4, 6, 7, 8, and 9 (continuing). Out of these five batches, only batches 4 and 6 have completed their education in 2021 and 2022.

In evaluating the program using the Kirkpatrick's Model, there are two aspects or levels: behavior and results. It is recommended that the evaluation implementation provide a sufficient time gap to determine whether the behavioral changes (behavior) of participants are permanent or not. Additionally, it is necessary to assess the tangible impact (results) of participants after completing the program.

Therefore, considering that only one batch, namely batch 4, has graduated within 2 years since the training ended in 2021, the subjects of this study are only the Teacher Empowerers of Batch 4 in South Tangerang, totaling

58 individuals. To validate the data collected from these Teacher Empowerers, the researcher will also include the subjects of this study, namely the school principal, 2 colleagues of the Teacher Empowerers, and 3 students of the Teacher Empowerers.

In collecting the data, the researcher will utilize observation techniques, questionnaires, and interviews, with the following explanations for each: a) The questionnaire given will still adhere to the principles of qualitative research, with open-ended questions. The questionnaire will be distributed to the 58 Teacher Empowerers of Batch 4 in South Tangerang using the Google Form application; b) Observation activities in this study will take place in the schools of the Teacher Empowerers of Batch 4 in South Tangerang (selected through purposive sampling based on questionnaire results), with the aim of observing the behavior and transformative educational efforts carried out by the Teacher Empowerers of Batch 4 in their respective schools; c) To confirm previously obtained data, the researcher will conduct interviews with selected respondents (based on purposive sampling from the questionnaire), the school principal, 2 colleagues, and 3 students of the teacher empowerers.

To test the validity of the data, the researcher will employ method triangulation, source triangulation, and theory triangulation, with the following explanations for each: (a) method triangulation - in this research, the data collection methods used by the researcher are sufficiently varied, where each method will confirm the others, namely document study, observation, and interviews; (b) source triangulation to ensure the accuracy of data/information obtained from the main respondents (Teacher Empowerers of Batch 4 regarding behavioral changes and transformative impacts in the school environment), the researcher will also conduct interviews with the school principal and 2 colleagues of the main respondents; and (c) theory triangulation - the researcher will use transformative theory or change theory to interpret the obtained data.

Referring to the data analysis based on Milles & Huberman's opinion (1994: 98-115), the steps taken by the researcher in data analysis are as follows: (a) data reduction, where the researcher collects, summarizes, and selects relevant data for the research questions; (b) reviewing/analyzing the summarized data, then processing and analyzing it based on available supporting data; (c) data verification, which involves interpreting the data and supplementing it by searching for needed data sources until the obtained data becomes saturated; (d) drawing conclusions as a result of the outlined methods.

RESEARCH RESULT

Overview of the Teacher Empowerment Program Batch 4 in South Tangerang:

The Teacher Empowerment Program is a professional development activity through education, training, and mentoring that focuses on instructional leadership to encourage the holistic development of students; actively and proactively develop other educators to implement student-centered learning; and serve as role models and agents of transformation in the education ecosystem to realize the profile of Pancasila students who are faithful, devout to the Almighty, have noble character, are creative,

collaborative, embrace global diversity, think critically, and are independent (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2021).

This Teacher Empowerment Program is implemented by the Teacher Empowerment Center as the Technical Implementation Unit of the Ministry of Education and collaborates with the local Department of Education and Culture. Up to this point, the Ministry of Education and Culture has conducted the Teacher Empowerment Program five times for the South Tangerang region, namely batches 4, 6, 7, 8, and 9 (continuing). Batch 4 Teacher Empowerers in South Tangerang, who are the subjects of this study, represent the first batch in the city.

The Teacher Empowerment Program Batch 4 in South Tangerang is attended by 58 teachers who completed the education for +9 months in 2021. The composition includes 22 male teachers and 36 female teachers, distributed across different educational levels: 5 from kindergarten, 21 from elementary school, 12 from junior high school, and 20 from high school/vocational school.

According to Regulation No. 26 of 2022 concerning the Teacher Empowerment Program issued by the Ministry of Education and Culture, this program aims to produce teachers with the profile of "Teacher Empowerer," possessing the ability to: (1) Plan, implement, assess, and reflect on learning that meets the current and future needs of students based on data; (2) Collaborate with parents, colleagues, and the community to develop the vision, mission, and programs of the educational unit; (3) Develop competencies independently and sustainably based on reflection on learning practices; and (4) Cultivate a learning ecosystem through reflection, collaboration, sports, and collective thinking with colleagues and the community voluntarily.

With reference to the above program objectives, the sub-focus examined using the Kirkpatrick model, specifically at level 3 related to behavior and level 4 related to results or impact, can be classified as follows:

1. Regarding the behavioral changes of Teacher Empowerers after participating in education:
 - a. Creating enjoyable and meaningful learning that accommodates the learning needs of students based on data.
 - b. Desire to develop competencies independently.
 - c. Willingness to collaborate and develop the learning ecosystem in their respective educational units.
2. Regarding the results/impact provided by Teacher Empowerers in their respective educational units after participating in education:
 - a. Fulfillment of enjoyable and meaningful learning needs for students.
 - b. Growth of the learning ecosystem in their respective educational units.

Regarding Behavioral Changes in Presenting Enjoyable and Meaningful Learning that Accommodates Student Needs

Based on the questionnaire responses from 35 Teacher Empowerers, data was obtained indicating that all of them experienced positive behavioral changes, particularly in presenting enjoyable and meaningful learning centered on students. The details are as follows: a) 13 teachers implemented

differentiated learning according to the students' profiles; b) 9 teachers provided enjoyable learning experiences; c) 5 teachers activated students in the classroom; d) 4 teachers showed enthusiasm in teaching; e) 2 teachers always engaged in post-learning reflection for future improvement.

To validate the accuracy of the above data, the researcher conducted method triangulation and source triangulation, namely by observing the Teacher Empowerers' schools and interviewing the School Principal and 3 students from Teacher Empowerers selected by the researcher (purposive sampling) based on questionnaire responses. The selected Teacher Empowerers were from SDN Pondok Ranji 04, SDN Cilenggang 2, and SDN Muncul 01.

Based on the observations at these four schools, it is evident that students of Teacher Empowerers are highly enthusiastic about learning, classrooms are very active, two-way teaching is implemented by the teachers, and the presented learning is enjoyable without causing pressure on the students. This is further confirmed through interviews with 3 students from each Teacher Empowerer. Overall, all students expressed a positive impression of their teachers' teaching methods, thoroughly enjoying the teaching styles.

Furthermore, based on interviews with the School Principals of each Teacher Empowerer, positive behavioral changes related to teaching were also confirmed. The positive impressions were also conveyed by the School Principals of each Teacher Empowerer. This was evident during academic supervision conducted by the School Principals, where class engagement and student happiness were clearly visible.

Based on these findings, the positive behavioral changes related to student-centered learning experienced by Teacher Empowerers after participating in the Teacher Empowerment Program are indeed valid.

Regarding Behavioral Changes in the Desire to Develop Competencies Independently

Based on the questionnaire responses from 35 Teacher Empowerers, data was obtained indicating that all of them have a desire to develop competencies independently, whether through online platforms such as the Merdeka Mengajar (Freedom to Teach) Platform or through offline training. The activities for competence enhancement varied, including literacy, numeracy, technology and information, practical teaching, STEAM, and others.

To validate the accuracy of the above data, the researcher conducted method triangulation and source triangulation, namely by interviewing the selected School Principal (purposive sampling) from the Teacher Empowerers at SDN Pondok Ranji 04, SDN Cilenggang 2, and SDN Muncul 01. Based on the interviews with these School Principals, it was confirmed that, in general, Teacher Empowerers have a high enthusiasm for learning and continually strive to develop their capacities and competencies.

Regarding Behavioral Changes in the Desire to Collaborate and Develop the Learning Ecosystem in Each Educational Unit

Based on the questionnaire responses from 35 Teacher Empowerers, data was obtained indicating that the majority of Teacher Empowerers have the

desire and have made efforts to cultivate the learning ecosystem in their respective schools.

Teacher Empowerers of Batch 4 in South Tangerang have made various efforts to foster a culture of learning (learning ecosystem) among their peers at their respective schools. This includes forming learning communities within the school, sharing best practices, and other initiatives.

The efforts made by these Teacher Empowerers have received positive responses from their peers. Some respondents mentioned an improvement in the learning culture among their peers, although it may not be optimal. This is partly due to the lack of support from the School Principal, including issues related to the availability of facilities and infrastructure.

To validate the accuracy of the above data, the researcher conducted method triangulation and source triangulation, namely by interviewing the School Principal and 2 peers of the Teacher Empowerers selected by the researcher (purposive sampling), namely, Teacher Empowerers from SDN Pondok Ranji 04, SDN Cilenggang 2, and SDN Muncul 01.

Based on the interviews with the School Principals of each Teacher Empowerer, it was generally conveyed that the Teacher Empowerers have indeed made efforts to encourage the growth of the learning ecosystem among the teachers. Although not optimal yet, there is an increased awareness among teachers to continue learning and improving. Similarly, the peers of the Teacher Empowerers also expressed appreciation for the initiatives taken by the Teacher Empowerers in fostering a learning culture among the teachers.

Regarding the Results/Impact Provided by Teacher Empowerers on Fulfilling Enjoyable and Meaningful Learning Needs of Students

As analyzed in point 1 above, all Teacher Empowerers of Batch 4 in South Tangerang have exhibited positive behavior related to delivering enjoyable and meaningful learning centered on students, accommodating the learning needs of each student. To test the accuracy of this data, the researcher conducted method triangulation and source triangulation, namely by observing the Teacher Empowerer schools and interviewing the School Principal and 3 students from the Teacher Empowerers selected by the researcher (purposive sampling), namely, Teacher Empowerers from SDN Pondok Ranji 04, SDN Cilenggang 2, and SDN Muncul 01.

Based on the observations in these four schools, it is evident that students of the Teacher Empowerers are highly enthusiastic about learning, the classrooms are very active, and the teaching is interactive. This was also confirmed based on interviews with three students from each Teacher Empowerer. Overall, all students had a positive impression of the way their teachers conducted classes, enjoying their teaching methods.

Furthermore, based on interviews with the School Principals of each Teacher Empowerer, positive behavioral changes related to teaching were also confirmed. Positive impressions were also conveyed by the School Principals of each Teacher Empowerer. This was particularly evident during academic

supervision conducted by the School Principal, where the class's activity and the students' happiness were clearly visible.

Considering these factors, the impact provided by Teacher Empowerers in delivering enjoyable, meaningful, and student-centered learning is indeed real and felt by the students.

Regarding the Results/Impact Provided by Teacher Empowerers on the Growth of the Learning Ecosystem in Each Educational Unit

As analyzed in point 3 above, all Teacher Empowerers have endeavored to foster a culture of learning among the teachers in their respective schools, such as by forming learning communities within the school and inviting teachers to regularly share best practices related to teaching every week, among other initiatives. This was also confirmed by the School Principal and peers of the Teacher Empowerers. The learning culture among the peers has indeed fostered a learning ecosystem in the schools of the Teacher Empowerers.

Although there is information conveyed by respondents that the learning ecosystem has not yet grown maximally, there is an increased awareness among teachers to continue learning and enhance their competencies to deliver contextualized teaching. Some obstacles include a lack of support from the school principal. Therefore, full support from the school principal is crucial. Teacher Empowerers cannot function effectively without the support of their school principals.

DISCUSSION

Teachers, as the vanguard of education, should be the primary actors in realizing higher-quality education by delivering high-quality, enjoyable, meaningful, and student-centered learning. Therefore, a culture of learning among teachers is essential to enable them to provide relevant and contextualized education in the current era where students find themselves. Hence, teachers are lifelong learners. However, the reality in the field reveals that some teachers are reluctant to learn. In some schools, there is no culture of learning among the teachers. Learning is seen as something exclusively for students, not for teachers.

This prevalent stigma among teachers must be changed. One of the strategies created by the Ministry of Education and Culture is to encourage teachers to take responsibility for the progress of education. These are teachers who are motivated, willing to take on a role to initiate and cultivate a learning culture, thus creating a learning ecosystem in their schools. This environment enables teachers to enhance the quality of their teaching.

Teacher Empowerers are not superior to other teachers; they are simply teachers willing to take on the crucial responsibility for the transformation of education. They encourage other teachers to grow, fostering a growth mindset, promoting a willingness to learn continuously, and making students, with all their strengths and weaknesses, the focal point of their learning objectives. Thus, teachers whose hearts are moved to participate in the Teacher Empowerer Education are intensively trained for approximately 6-9 months through online and offline methods, equipped with various knowledge to instill

the motivation and ability to inspire other teachers, especially within their school environment.

The Teacher Empowerer Education Program with a bottom-up approach that positions teachers as key figures and agents of educational transformation has proven to be quite effective. The research conducted by the investigator shows that Teacher Empowerers have indeed succeeded in delivering enjoyable, meaningful, and student-centered learning in their classrooms, fostering the character of Pancasila learners. Moreover, they have demonstrated the ability to develop a learning ecosystem in their schools, despite facing numerous challenges.

Obstacles in implementing educational transformation can indeed arise within the school environment itself. According to the research findings, some respondents expressed that a lack of support from the school's leadership is one of the hindrances. Referring to the change theory presented by McShane and Glinow, what the respondents conveyed is highly relevant and accurate.

According to McShane and Glinow (2008:492), the general process of change consists of three stages: unfreezing, changing, and refreezing. This process explains how the current situation is altered and moved towards the desired condition, which is then established as a new system or renewal to be sustained as an enduring culture. The illustration is as follows:

McShane and Glinow (2008:492) explain the flow above that by referring to the "unfreezing" process of the current situation, it can be accomplished if the driving force of change is greater than the force resisting change. This explanation implies that organizational change can be pursued when change leaders can choose among three approaches: increasing the driving force of change more than the force resisting change, weakening or eliminating the force resisting change, or combining both approaches simultaneously.

If the choice falls on the first approach, then change leaders must enhance the driving force to motivate the occurrence of change. However, change very rarely happens by only increasing the driving force because the force resisting change will always balance the driving force of change. This condition aligns with the law of system dynamics that the more force is applied to a system, the stronger the resisting force is to push back. This phenomenon is captured by the saying, "The harder you push, the harder the system pushes back" (Senge, 2004:43). Such antagonism can actually threaten change efforts as it generates tension and conflict within the organization. According to McShane, the best option is to combine efforts to strengthen the driving force and simultaneously weaken or even eliminate the resisting force to change.

Referring to this theory, the transformation efforts made by Teacher Empowerers in changing the paradigms of other teachers may not proceed optimally if there are obstacles, including the lack of full support from school leadership. Therefore, the step taken by the Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbudristek) to appoint Teacher Empowerers as educational leaders (school principals or supervisors) is an attempt to combine both ways: strengthening the driving force and weakening the resisting force. Teacher Empowerers, who will later become school principals, will have full authority

to motivate their teachers in realizing quality education, providing full support for educational transformation, and eliminating all obstacles in their schools.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research conducted by the researcher using the Kirkpatrick model on the implementation of the Teacher Empowerment Program Batch 4 South Tangerang, specifically regarding behavioral changes and the impact of Teacher Empowerers on the improvement of teaching quality and the growth of the learning ecosystem in schools, the following points are conveyed:

1. There are positive behavioral changes among Teacher Empowerers of Batch 4 South Tangerang. This includes the desire to continue providing enjoyable and meaningful learning centered on students, the desire to keep learning and developing competencies to enhance teaching quality, and fostering a culture of learning among fellow teachers in their schools.
2. There is a positive impact from the presence of Teacher Empowerers in their schools. Based on observations and interviews with students, it is clear that students are happy and enthusiastic about learning in class because Teacher Empowerers provide enjoyable learning tailored to the students' learning profiles. Not only that, the learning ecosystem for teachers is also beginning to grow. This is confirmed by interviews with school principals and colleagues of Teacher Empowerers.

The Teacher Empowerment Program has proven to be effective in producing teachers with the ability to provide higher quality, enjoyable, and meaningful learning centered on students. It also equips teachers with the ability to motivate and inspire their fellow teachers within the school's ecosystem to adopt a new paradigm in interpreting the meaning of learning – emphasizing that learning is not just for students but also for teachers. This ensures that teachers consistently deliver relevant and contextual learning in line with the era in which the students exist.

The positive behavioral changes observed in Teacher Empowerers after participating in the Teacher Empowerment Program clearly impact the improvement of teaching quality in classrooms and the growth of a culture of learning among teachers within the school's ecosystem. Although there are some schools where the growth of the culture of learning among their teachers is not yet optimal, they are moving towards improvement. Every transformation effort will face challenges and obstacles. Therefore, the step taken by the Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbudristek) to appoint Teacher Empowerers as leaders of educational units is very appropriate. This is to strengthen the driving force for change and simultaneously reduce resistance or rejection of change.

A program with a bottom-up approach, such as the Teacher Empowerment Program, should continue its existence under any government leadership, as the program's goals have been successfully implemented. This program has proven to be effective in producing agents of change in realizing educational transformation, especially at the smallest level, namely within schools. The presence, role, and activities of Teacher Empowerers as agents of

transformation are crucial in the change strategy, particularly to strengthen the driving force and simultaneously weaken or eliminate the resistance to change.

The Central Government, in this case, the Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbudristek), needs to encourage each Regional Government to promptly appoint Teacher Empowerers in their areas as school principals, in accordance with the regulations. This is solely to lead the school transformation process towards a comprehensive improvement in the quality of education, including eliminating resistance to change within schools.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Based on these findings, bottom-up approaches like PPGP should continue to exist, regardless of the government's leadership. The program has proven effective in producing agents of change in transforming education, especially at the school level. The presence, role, and activities of teacher mover as transformation agents are crucial in change strategies, particularly to strengthen driving forces and weaken or eliminate resistance to change. The central government, represented by the Ministry of Education and Culture, should encourage every local government to promptly appoint teacher mover as school principals, as mandated by regulations. This step is essential to lead the school transformation process towards a more comprehensive improvement in education quality, including removing resistance to change within schools.

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